

A Geographical Analysis of the Literacy Pattern in Maharashtra's Parbhani District

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Introduction:

Literacy is essential for eradicating poverty and mental isolation for cultivating peaceful and friendly international relations and for permitting the free play of demographic process (Chandna and Singh, 1980. P.98). The variation in literacy many times indicates the place of which a society is getting transform. A level of literacy influences to a significant extent the socio- economic development of a region. Literacy also influences fertility mortality and economic composition of the population of a region levels of literacy vary enormously from one country to other. Even with the same country the level of literacy vary between urban and rural areas among male and females and also different occupational and social groups a large numbers of socio- economic factors such as nature of economy level of urbanization, standard of living place of female in society, education opportunities and levels of technological development influences the literacy pattern. The trends in literacy are considered an index of the pace at which the socio-economic transformation of a society is taking place.

The Indian census considers a person literate if one can both read and write with understanding in any language. The literacy rate of the state as whole was 76.90 percent in 2001. About 67 percent population of the study region was literate in 2001. It is 9.90 percent less than the state average.

Objectives:

The major object of this paper is to study the population literacy on spatial- Temporal – variation in literacy of Parbhani district of Maharashtra.

Study Region:

Parbhani district is situated in the central of Maharashtra and lies between 18 45'North to 20 01' North latitudes and 76 13'East to 77 26' East Longitudes. The boundaries attached to the neighboring districts on north by Buldhana and Akola, on east by Hingoli and Nanded, on south Latur and Beed and on west Jalna district. The river Purna runs on the boundaries of Hingoli and Parbhani district and work as attach these two regions. The other River Godavari which runs on the

boundaries of Beed and Parbhani forms a part of study region. It runs through Pathri, Sonpeth, Manwat, Gangakhed, Palam and Purna tahsils. The area of study region is 6511 sq. kms, which is 2.11 percent of the total area of the state. The population of the study region is 1491109 (2001 census) which is 2.76 percent of the total population is 229 persons per sq.km. Among the thirty five districts of the state, the district ranks 26th in terms of population and 18th in terms of density. The region includes 830 inhabited villages and eight urban centers. The study region is administratively subdivided into nine tahsils namely Parbhani, Gangakhed, Palam, Sonpeth, Purna, Pathri, Manwat, Sailu, and Jintur. (Fig no.1)

Fig no.1

Date Base and Methodology:

The present paper is based on secondary sources. i.e. district census handbook, socio-

economic abstract, etc. suitable statistical techniques are used in the present paper. The period from 1991 to 2011 is selected for observation. The result has

been shown with the help of different graphs, tables, and maps.

Explanation : Literacy of Parbhani district studied by two patterns i.e.- temporal literacy change and spatial literacy pattern.

Table 1-Percentage of literates to total population in Parbhani District 1991-2011

Sr. No.	Tahsil	1991	2001	2011	Change in 1991 to 2011
1	Parbhani	59.83	70.09	79.19	19.36
2	Gangakhed	59.78	62.71	74.22	14.44
3	Palam	61.53	61.53	73.72	12.19
4	Sonpeth	56.45	58.38	71.42	14.97
5	Purna	60.55	63.66	75.09	14.54
6	Pathri	57.33	61.39	72.62	15.29
7	Manwat	58.78	62.10	73.71	14.93
8	Sailu	57.48	61.27	72.86	15.38
9	Jintur	59.26	61.70	73.54	14.28
	Total	59.25	64.27	75.22	15.04

Literacy pattern in Parbhani District:

The percentage of literate to the total population for 1991, 2001, and 2011 have been calculated for temporal variation in tahsil wise literacy pattern of the Parbhani district.

Literacy Pattern in 1991 Year:

The average literacy for the region was 59.25% in 1991 being the highest for the Palam tahsil while the lowest was for Sonpeth tahsil. There are only five tahsils that show a higher percentage of literates than the region average these are Parbhani, Gangakhed, Palam, Purna, and Jintur. The rest of the other tahsil represents a low percentage of literates than the region average in the year 1991.

Literacy Pattern in 2001 Year:

For the year 2001, the total literacy for the district was 64.27% Parbhani tahsil again retained the first position as regards the population of literates while lowest again for the Sonpeth tahsil. In this year there was only one tahsil i.e.Parbhani which was above the regional average for literacy while the rest of other tahsils represent a lower percentage of literates below the area for the region

Literacy Pattern in 2011 Year:

In most decades 2011 due to social awareness among the people remarkable

percentages of literate were recorded in the year 2011. For the district as a whole, the percentage of the literates was observed at 75.22 percent, In this year there was the highest literacy in Parbhani tahsil while the lowest was for the Sonpeth tahsil. In this decade due to social awareness among the people most of the tahsils of Parbhani district have recorded a very high percentage of literate in most of the tahsil and as a result of this, there are not so wide variations in the literacy rate within the different tahsil of the Parbhani. It may be stated that primary education facilities are being made compulsory by the Government in order to improve the standard of living of the people. This has been also observed that now day present living in rural areas is taking an increasing interest. To teach their children without making a distinction between male and female children.

Overall change in literacy pattern of Parbhani:

The literacy of the Parbhani district tremendously increasing in the last decades the rate of growth varies from tahsil to tahsil in the study region. It is also influenced by many environmental as well as socio-economic and cultural factors.

Overall change in literacy pattern of Parbhani District 1991-2011

Sr. No.		No. Of Tahsil	Name of the Tahsil
01	High (Above 25%)	02	Parbhani
02	Moderate (15% to 20%)	03	Pathri, Sailu, Sonpeth, Manwat, Gangakhed, Purna, Jintur
03	Low (below 15%)	01	Palam

The table clearly shows that the high literacy is Parbhani tahsil of Parbhani district. Increasing the educational facilities increasing economic states connectivity of village to town and people's attitude towards life is responsible for high increasing literacy rule moderate literacy observed in Pathri, Sailu, Sonpeth, Manwat, Gangakhed, Purna, Jintur in the study region. In this region lack of transport necessary for low economic states does

not good tendency toward female literacy. The low increasing rate is observed in the Palam tahsil of the district but the total literacy of this region is actually high in this tahsil. These tahsils are well developed and major cities are located in this region.

Conclusion:

This paper studies the spatial-temporal variation in the literacy pattern of the Parbhani district. These variations can be attributed to social

cultural and economic factors that severely impact on literacy of the district high literacy is observed in Parbhani and low in Sonpeth tahsil of the district. The comparative study is four decades shows an increase in literacy slightly. The rate of literacy varies from tahsil to tahsil in the Parbhani district for increasing literacy, especially in the rural area need to provide transport facilities, totally free education, and strong protection.

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